

THE LOW VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH GRADED FOAM CORES

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ABSTRACT

The low velocity impact response of sandwich structures with graded foams cores have been investigated both experimentally and numerically. Sandwich structures, based on graded foams, were fabricated by bonding carbon fibre skins and three foam sheets with differing densities. Twelve combinations of graded foam core were investigated based on a range of crosslinked PVC, liner PVC and PEI foams. The structures were loaded by a drop-weight impact carriage with a hemispherical projectile and the load-displacement traces were recorded. The dynamic response of the panels was characterised by determining the energy required to perforate the target. The impact responses of the panels were also predicted using the finite element technique.

The failure modes in the graded sandwich structures were examined and it was observed that many panels fractured in a through-thickness shearing mode, leaving a cylindrical hole in the graded foam cores. A mixed tensile/shear mode was also observed resulting in cone cracking on the exit surface in a limited number of panels. The most impressive structures were those associated with placing a high density foam core at the top surface, a low density foam in the centre and a ductile foam at the rear surface. The FE model produces the predictions of both the load-displacement responses and the perforation energies of the structures accurately. The predictions have also been used to demonstrate that graded foam core can out-perform their monolithic counterparts in terms of their impact resistance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent specific properties, sandwich structures have been extensively used in a wide range of lightweight structural roles, such as the aircraft, maritime, and automotive industries. The response of sandwich structures subject to impact loading has been summarized in a review by Chai and Zhu [1]. Qiao et al [2] provide a brief overview for the research on impact mechanics and high-energy absorbing materials using different theoretical and computational methods. Lin and Hoo Fatt [3] used an analytical model to predict the low velocity impact response of glass/epoxy-aluminium honeycomb panels. A three-stage perforation model was used that considered failure of the top composite skin, the honeycomb core and the lowermost composite skin. The perforation model predicted the perforation velocity of the panel under low velocity impact conditions.

Although a number of experimental works has been conducted to study the impact and blast response of sandwich beams and panels, a few of workers have attempted to simulate the perforation behaviour of such structures under impact loading. Zhou *et al* [4] investigated perforation resistance in foam-based sandwich panels using the finite element analysis technique. The FE analysis accurately predicted the impact load-displacement responses and the perforation energies of both the plain foams and the sandwich panels. The FE analysis was used to investigate the effect of oblique loading on sandwich structures and to study the impact response of sandwich panels on an aqueous support as well. Buitrago *et al* [5] used finite element techniques to model the impact perforation process in sandwich panels based on an aluminium honeycomb and core carbon fibre/epoxy skins. They showed that most of the incident energy of the projectile was absorbed by the 2 mm thick composite skins, with the core absorbing between ten and twenty percent of the impact energy.

A number of theoretical analyses and numerical studies have been carried out to investigate the dynamic response of functionally-graded foam sandwich structures. Etemadi *et al* [6] developed a 3-D finite element model to model sandwich panels with functionally-graded cores subjected to low velocity impact loading. The effect of varying the projectile velocity and kinetic energy, as well as the influence of beam dimensions on the impact behaviour and associated indentation and displacement histories have been investigated studied using validated models. Cui *et al* [7] proposed a functionally-graded foam model and studied its energy-absorbing characteristics using the finite element method. It was shown that functionally-graded foams are superior in their energy-absorbing capability than plain foams and that convex gradients perform better than concave systems. Sburlati [8] presented an elastic bending analysis for circular sandwich panels with exponentially-graded material cores. The solution associated sensitivity analyses highlighted the advantages of graded cores in reducing interfacial stresses, thereby decreasing the likelihood of failure. Avila [9] developed a failure criterion to simulate piece-wise functionally-graded sandwich composites and the failure mechanisms have been predicted successfully to against the experimental data. The most impressive performance was exhibited by a beam configuration in which the highest density core was located directly below the upper face-sheet. Icardi and Ferero [10] investigated performance of sandwich panels with functionally-graded core and faces. The distribution of properties through the thickness (core) and in-plane (face sheets) that minimise the interlaminar stresses at the interface with the core were optimised in their study.

The aim of this study is to investigate the impact behaviour of layered foam-based sandwich structures made with a range of PVC and PEI foam cores and carbon fibre resin plastic (CFRP) face sheets. The low velocity impact response of the sandwich panels is predicted using three dimensional non-linear finite element models to investigate the influence of core configurations and properties on the perforation resistance of the foam based sandwich structures. Attention is given to identifying the fundamental parameters that govern the impact response of these graded structures.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Graded foam based sandwich structures were made with carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) face sheets and graded/layered foam cores fabricated by bonding foams with different densities together. Core materials with varying through the thickness properties were manufactured by bonding three 10 mm thick foam panels together using a fast-drying contact adhesive. The carbon fibre skins were then bonded to the core, as shown schematically in Figure 1. A range of linear PVC, crosslinked PVC and PEI foams were bonded together to produce a three layer core. Table 1 summarises the properties of the nine different foams investigated in this study. Four of the foams were based on crosslinked PVC foams with densities between 60 and 200 kg/m³. The three linear PVC foams have densities between 60 and 140 kg/m³ and the two PEI foams offered densities of 60 and 80 kg/m³. Table 2 summarises the stacking sequences of the twelve configurations and, in which the average core density varied from approximately 77 kg/m³ to 113 kg/m³. Prior to testing, the 0.35 mm thick skins were manufactured by stacking two woven CFRP plies (EP121 C15-53 from Gurit Ltd) and

heated up to 125 °C for an hour. The graded cores and carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) skins were bonded together using a two-part epoxy resin.

Figure 1 Sketch of configurations of graded foam core based sandwiches

Table 1 Mechanical properties of the foams investigated in this research

Mechanical properties	C60	C80	C100	C200	L60	L90	L140	P60	P80
Density (kg/m ³)	60	80	100	200	30	90	140	60	80
Poisson's ratio	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32
Compressive modulus (MPa)	69	97	125	280	30	56	110	46	62
Compressive strength (MPa)	0.9	1.3	1.9	4.8	0.38	0.9	1.6	0.7	1.1
Compressive fracture strain	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
Tensile modulus (MPa)	45	66	84	175	30	50	90	45	54
Tensile strength (MPa)	1.3	2	2.7	6	0.9	1.4	2.4	1.7	2.0
Shear modulus (MPa)	22	30	38	75	11	21	37	18	23
Shear strength (MPa)	0.8	1.2	1.6	3.5	0.5	1	1.85	0.8	1.1
Shear fracture strain	0.16	0.23	0.27	0.3	0.7	0.75	0.8	0.25	0.23
Work of fracture in tension (kJ/m ²)	0.26	0.44	0.62	1.33	2.38	6.06	12.1	0.87	15.8
Work of fracture in shear (kJ/m ²)	6.48	12.6	18.4	44.2	17.3	21.3	27.3	1.16	24.8

Low velocity impact tests were conducted on the sandwich structures to investigate perforation resistance using a drop-weight impact tower shown in Figure 2. Here, the 150 mm square panels (containing eight bolt holes along their edges) were placed on a 100 mm long steel cylinder. The panels were impacted centrally by a carriage with a 10 mm diameter hemispherical head. The mass of the impactor was 5.56 kg and the release height of the impact carriage was up to 1.4 metres. The impact force and displacement of the impactor were measured using a piezoelectric load cell and a high-speed video camera, respectively.

Table 2 Foam core configurations of the sandwiches investigated in this study.

Code	Configurations	Average density (kg/m ³)
C1	C100/P80/P60	80.0
C2	P60/P80/C100	80.0
C3	L80/C60/C200	113.3
C4	C200/C60/L80	113.3
C5	C80/L60/C100	76.7
C6	C100/L60/C80	76.7
C7	L60/P60/L140	86.7
C8	L140/P60/L60	86.7
C9	P80/P60/C200	113.3
C10	C200/P60/P80	113.3
C11	C60/L80/L140	93.3
C12	L140/L80/C60	93.3

After testing, the specimen panels were centrally sectioned through the perforated region, ground and then polished and photographed under an optical microscope to elucidate the failure mechanisms associated with the perforation process.

Figure 2 Schematic of drop-weight impact test

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Numerical models were developed to simulate the dynamic response of the graded foam sandwich panels subjected to low velocity impact loading. Prior to damage initiation, CFRP was modelled as an orthotropic elastic material. The in-plane longitudinal and transverse moduli of elasticity were assumed to be equal since the CFRP skins were based on a plain weave. Damage initiation was modelled using Hashin's failure criteria [11] which assume four damage initiation mechanisms, namely fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression. Using the longitudinal, transverse and shear effective stress tensor components within the plane of the CFRP, the damage initiation criteria can be determined [12]. Damage evolution is modelled by the negative slope of the equivalent stress-displacement relation after damage initiation is achieved. The fracture energies for fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression failure modes need to be specified to indicate the energy dissipated during damage development.

The foam under compression was modelled as a crushable foam material for which the hardening curve was determined from a foam compression test. Deshpande and Fleck [13] proposed a phenomenological yield surface for these closed-cell foams as given by

$$\phi \equiv \frac{1}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right)^2\right]} \left[q^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_m^2 \right] - \sigma_y^2 \leq 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ_y is the uniaxial tensile or compressive yield strength of the foam, σ_m is the mean stress, q is the Von Mises stress. In Eq. (1), α defines the shape of the yield surface, which is related to the ratios of the initial uniaxial yield stress (σ_c^o) and the hydrostatic tensile yield stress (p_t) to the hydrostatic compressive yield stress (p_c^o), respectively. The yield stress (p_c) in hydrostatic compression provides the evolution of the yield surface size and can be expressed as:

$$p_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) = \frac{\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left[\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^2} + \frac{1}{9} \right) + \frac{p_t}{3} \right]}{p_t + \frac{\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol})}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where ε_{pl}^{vol} is the plastic volumetric strain for the volumetric hardening model, which is equal to ε_{pl}^{axial} , uniaxial compressive plastic strain. Therefore, p_c should be determined from a uniaxial compression test on the foam.

The resin layers between the composite skins and the cores were modelled using cohesive elements [14]. The maximum nominal stress and the effective displacement following a linear softening law were employed to simulate the mechanisms of damage initiation and progression respectively. The general contact interaction was included between the CFRP skin faces and foam cores to simulate the case where the cohesive layer is damaged by projectile. A surface-to-surface contact interaction was employed between the node set of the target centre of the constituent layers of the sandwich and the projectile surface to allow for finite sliding during perforation. In addition, tie constraint were defined between all adjacent layers of sandwich to restore the interaction between each skin and the core layers.

A fully-clamped sandwich panel, based on three layered foam cores, was modelled using ABAQUS/Explicit. The geometry as well as the boundary and loading conditions for the sandwich panel are shown in Figure 3. A rigid cylindrical projectile was employed. The initial projectile velocity was set to that based on the perforation energy obtained from the experimental tests. One half of the panel was modelled since the panel was symmetric. The foam and were skin meshed using continuum shell elements (SC8R) and eight-noded reduced integration elements (C3D8R) respectively.

Figure 3 The geometry, mesh, boundary and loading conditions of the graded foam sandwich model.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Low velocity impact simulations were undertaken on the twelve core configurations. Figure 4(a) shows a comparison between the experimental (solid lines) and FE predicted (dashed lines) load-displacement trace for a sandwich panel based on the L60/P60/L140 foam combination. The experimental trace exhibits a number of distinct regions as the projectile passes through the various components of the sandwich panel. An examination of the figure indicates that the initial portion of the trace is linear up to approximately 480 Newtons, at which point the top surface skin fractures and the load drops. The force then oscillates around a value of approximately 410 Newtons, as the projectile passes through the tough L60 foam. The force then reduces as the impactor passes through the P60 foam before increasing rapidly as it encounters the L140 foam. The final stage of the load-displacement trace exhibits a region in which the force oscillates as the L140 foam is crushed and densifies under the constraint applied by the rear surface skin. From the comparison of the curves it is clear that the model captures all of the major features of the experimental trace, including the pronounced second peak associated with the crushing of the core against the distal skin. Figure 4(b) shows cross-sections of the fully perforated sandwich structures, where the presence of a distinct cylindrically-shaped shear zone is evident in both the test specimen and the model.

Figure 4(c) shows the measured and predicted load-displacement traces for the equivalent inverted structure, i.e. the L140/P60/ L60 core configuration. Clearly, with the perforation force increasing in three steps between the peaks associated with fracturing the upper and lower skins. The plateau force resulting from fracturing the tough L140 foam is significantly higher than that required to perforate its lower density P60 counterpart. The cross-section of the perforated sandwich structures as shown in Figure 4(d). Once again, agreement between the predicted and measured load-displacement curves is generally good, although the model fails to identify the brittle failure mode in the top skin.

Figure 4 Load-displacement traces and resulting cross-sections for (a, b) the L60/P60/L140 sandwich structure and (c, d) for the L140/P60/L60 sandwich structure.

Figures 5(a) and 5(c) show the experimental and numerical load-displacement traces for the L80/C60/C200 sandwich structure and the equivalent inverted structure. The experimental trace exhibits a number of distinct regions as the projectile passes through the various components of the sandwich panel. Clearly, there are similarities between this response and that shown in Figure 4(a) and 4(c), with the perforation force increasing in three steps between the peaks associated with fracturing the upper and lower skins. The plateau force resulting from fracturing the tough C200 foam is significantly higher than that required to perforate its lower density L80 counterpart.

The measured and predicted failure mode for the corresponding sandwich structure are shown in Figure 5(b). Figure 5(d) highlight the presence of a crack in the uppermost C200 foam that appears to have influenced the subsequent failure locus in the remainder of the structure. This mixed form of failure has been partly captured by the FE model. Here, the different fracture responses of the three foams are apparent, with the uppermost, high density C200 foam offering the greatest resistance to perforation and the more brittle C60 system exhibiting the lowest. The resulting cross-section from the test, Figure 5(d), highlights the presence of a crack in the uppermost C200 foam that appears to have influenced the subsequent failure locus in the remainder of the structure. Once again, agreement

between the experimental data and the model is very good, suggesting that the FE analysis is capable of capturing the fundamental response of these multi-layered structures.

Figure 5 Load-displacement traces and resulting cross-sections for (a, b) the L80/C60/C200 sandwich structure and (c, d) for the C200/C60/L80 sandwich structure.

The energy required to perforate the sandwich panels was calculated by determining the area under the load-displacement traces. The perforation resistances of the twelve configurations were compared in Figure 6. From the figure, it is clear that the FE model generally predicts the energy required to perforate the laminates with a high degree of accuracy, with the greatest error being approximately fourteen percent. The figure also shows that the perforation energy varies quite significantly, with the experimental values passing from 21.9 Joules for the C100/L60/C80 sandwich to 40.8 Joules for the C200/P60/P80 configuration. Within each density grouping of structures, there are distinct variations that depend on the specific arrangement of the layers. This is most evident in Panels C9 (P80/P60/C200) and C10 (C200/P60/P80) in which the former has the high density C200 core at the uppermost surface and latter at the bottom surface. It suggests that placing the higher density, tougher foam uppermost resulted in a 30% increase in the perforation resistance.

Figure 6 Comparison of the predicted and experimental perforation energies.

Figure 7 shows a plot of the perforation energy versus average target density, highlighting the benefit of placing the highest density foam on the top surface. An examination of the figure indicates that those laminates in which the highest density foam is placed uppermost tend to out-perform equivalent systems in which the higher density foam is placed against the rear surface skin. The figure also suggests that this enhancement tends to increase with increasing average foam density. Secondary benefits were also observed, such as placing the lowest density foam in the centre of the core and also placing a tough foam against the rear surface of the structure.

Figure 7 Comparison of perforation energy against the average core density between different core layer arrangements.

The perforation resistances of the various graded foam cores were compared with those of similar sandwich structures based on one single type of core, for example a C200/C200/C200 construction. Here, the perforation resistances of these “plain” core materials were predicted using the FE model, since previous work has shown that the perforation resistance of plain sandwich panels can be accurately predicted using this approach [4]. The predicted perforation energies of the single density crosslinked PVC sandwiches (with densities ranging from 60 to 200 kg/m³) are shown in Figure 8. The figure indicates that the graded foam core sandwich structures offer a superior perforation resistance to the equivalent monolithic cores.

Figure 8 Comparison of perforation energy between sandwich structures based on graded and single type foam cores.

Although performance is a key criterion in selecting a particular core for a given sandwich structure, cost is also an important parameter in the design process. Here, a cost factor was determined by normalising the cost of each foam by the cost of the most expensive foam tested here (this was the P80 foam) and then by multiplying this value by 100. The relative performance of each graded foam was then compared on a cost basis by dividing the perforation energy values by the cost factor, and these results are presented in Figure 9. An examination of the figure indicates that the perforation energy/cost ratio varies significantly across the range of structures considered. Of particular interest is Structure C5, based largely on low density foams. The performance of this sandwich structure outperforms Structures C1 and C2 by a factor of approximately four.

Figure 9 Comparison of cost performance between graded foam based sandwiches.

CONCLUSIONS

The low velocity impact response of sandwich structures based on layered cores has been studied both experimentally and numerically. Agreement between the predictions of the finite element models and the experimental results was very good across the range of structures in term of load-displacement traces, failure mode and the corresponding perforation energies. Failure in the majority of the sandwich structures occurred as a results of core shear, with the FE model accurately predicting this mode of failure. It has also been evidenced that graded structures can out-perform their monolithic

counterparts in terms of their perforation resistance. It has been suggested that placing the high density foam core against the top surface skin can lead to an improved perforation resistance relative to sandwich panels in which the higher density foam is in contact with the distal surface. More benefits associated with a ductile foam against the lower surface and placing the lowest density foam in the centre of the core have also been observed. Finally, significant differences are observed between the various core configurations when the unit cost of the various foams is considered.

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